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Title: IoT based Remote health Monitoring and Patients' early treatment using Arduino Uno

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Abstract

*Nowadays IoT is playing a vital role in different sectors such as healthcare centers in which patient's health status can be monitored remotely. Hospital is one of a health care institution providing patient treatment with specialized nursing staff and medical equipment for many people at once that leads over-crowding especially in countries with limited number of healthcare centers like Ethiopia, which evade the current rule of the government to save the life from covid-19. Therefore, most of our people cannot fully get the hospital services, even for other diseases such as blood pressure, heart beat, TB, and many others since they are staying at home. To solve these problems, we **propose IoT based remote health monitoring and patients' early treatment system using Arduino uno**. The system uses sensors placed at home to early collect the health status (disease symptoms) of a person and forward it to the ThingSpeak cloud. The hospital system can access patient data from the cloud to recommend appropriate drug (also possible precautions) and inform patient from their web portal through patient's mobile phone using either SMS or email alert, so that the patient with low risk disease can buy drugs nearby. If the health condition of a patient is at risk the system automatically schedule when and where he/she get the service of the hospital at center.*

Acronyms

RPHM: Remote Patient Health Monitoring

GPS: Global Positioning System

IEEE: International Electrical and Electronics Engineering.

IoT: Internet of Things.

USB: Universal Serial Bus

TB: Tuberculosis

PWM: Pulse Width Modulation

ICSP: In-circuit serial programming

SMS: Short Message Service

VLSI: Very-large-scale integration

ECG: Electrocardiogram

GSM: Global System for Mobile Communications

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1. Introduction

Health issue is becoming serious problem in developing countries like Ethiopia in which there are limited number of healthcare system and others health facilities like drug along with lack of specialized Doctor mostly in rural area. Most of the people living out there lose their life due to improper health monitoring systems. In this era of contaminated environment, concern about human health is top priority than ever before. If he/she feels unwell they need a medical checkup and their health should monitored continuously. In our country, only major cities have hospitals with full-time physicians, and most of the hospitals are located in Addis Ababa. Access to modern health care in many rural areas are virtually nonexistent [1]. As of Monday, June 29, 2020, based on Worldometer elaboration of the latest United Nations data, 78.7% of our people are living in rural areas [2]. They need health treatment.

Even though there are few numbers of healthcare center, it is unable to manage those with large number of populations with the existing number of Doctor and others medical equipment during this lockdown. This time is the worst time throughout the world because of corona virus cases. Due to covid-19, our people even don't get fully service of the existing the health care system than ever before since it leads overcrowding at hospital which supports covid-19 outbreak even more.

With the improvement of current emerging technology like Internet of thing those health problems can be solved efficiently. The Internet of Things (IoT) concepts have been widely used to interconnect the available medical resources and offer smart, reliable, and effective healthcare service to the patients. Health monitoring for active and assisted living is one of the paradigms that can use the IoT advantages to improve the patient's lifestyle [3]. Now question is how people get the service from hospital while they are staying home? It is possible with remote health monitoring system. So, **we propose IoT based remote health monitoring and patients' early treatment system using Arduino uno**. A remote patient monitoring system is one of the solutions to overcome the barriers of health service. It allows the doctor to observe the patient's health condition remotely at any time and any place [4].

The system allows us to get health service remotely from health center while staying at home using sensor and Arduino uno placed at home to early detect the status of the patient for disease such as blood pressure, heart beat, and TB including covid-19.

Patient Health monitoring using IoT is a technology to enable monitoring of patients outside of conventional clinical settings (e.g. in the home), which may increase access to care and decrease healthcare delivery costs. This can significantly improve an individual's quality of life. It allows patients to maintain independence, prevent complications, and minimize personal costs. This system facilitates these goals by delivering care right to the home. In addition, patients and their family members feel comfort knowing that they are being monitored and will be supported if a problem arises.

Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board which is based on Atmega 328P. It has 14 digital output/input pins. PWM outputs can be taken with 6 pins. It has a clock of 16 MHz Arduino can be easily interfaced with USB. Flash Memory of 32Kb provides the space for storing the programs. For directly interfacing Arduino as serial device ICSP header is present [5].

1.1 Research Questions

This work will try to answer the following research questions

How to design RPHM System efficiently?

How does this System combat Covid-19?

How does this System reduce the cost of regular checkup for patients with their Doctor?

How to solve health monitoring problems using RPHM System?

1.2 Motivation

Currently due to Covid-19 everyone staying at home because over-crowding of peoples is not allowed since it facilitates transmission of the disease. We observe many patients with different diseases which are at home and could not get fast treatment because hospitals are giving priority to serve Covid-19 patients since it is critical problem by which we are losing a number of lives daily. In addition to that government recommending stay at home principle, patients themselves face lack of confidence to go to healthcare center because there is fear of Covid-19 epidemic. Observing this problem, we suggest that there should a system in which patients should get early treatment while they are at home.

1.3 Statement of problem

Health monitoring is the most critical issue over the world currently. In developing countries like Ethiopia, it is difficult to serve many patients simultaneously since there is limited number of health centers. Having this problem all patients including those from rural areas should go to

hospitals for any kind of disease which makes overcrowding at the health center. But currently peoples are enforced to stay at home by government and also patients themselves choose to stay at home while they need treatment since there is fear of Covid-19. Some major problems we are facing due to lack of remote health monitoring includes:

- Wasting of time and effort as well as costs for patients for regular checkup at hospitals to know their health status and they have to wait for long time to be served due to limited number of patients can be served simultaneously because of Covid-19 transmission.
- It is difficult for patients to know their healthy status while they are at home
- Patients are over-crowded at hospitals which facilitates fast transmission of Covid-19.
- Patients even with a very low risk disease want to go to hospital to check their health status and facilitate over-crowding since there is no smart system that can recommend such patients to perform possible precautions rather than going to hospital every time.
- Patients faces lack of confidence and psychological problem since they couldn't know their health status while staying at home
- Cost of transportation

1.4 Objectives the system

1.4.1 General Objective

The main objective of this work is to address the problem of health issues in Ethiopia specially for those who live in rural areas to remotely provide possible treatments and reduce overcrowding of patient's at health centers by introducing IoT based remote health monitoring and patient's early treatment system using Arduino Uno.

1.4.2 Specific objectives

To achieve the above general objective, we will try to define the following specific goals:

- To address patient's health issue without going to hospitals
- To offers patients early treatment (recommending drugs and possible precautions)
- To reduces over crowd of patient at hospitals during this lockdown time or
- To fight the spread of Covid-19, in our country Ethiopia since patient can get fully service of hospitals while they are staying at home
- To notify patient's health status through their SMS or Email
- Uploading patient's sensor data to ThingSpeak cloud so that it is available for doctors

- Recommending patients to do possible precautions by system and also treatment information from doctors by sending them SMS.
- Writing Arduino program and setting a threshold for each parameter to identify and alarm weather the patient is at high risk.
- To Minimizes cost of transportation to the hospital
- To Saves the time and effort of the patient

1.5 Scope of the system

This System is designed for Ethiopian people specially for those who live in rural areas where there are limited number of specialized doctor and others health facilities like medical equipment during covid-19. The system will be applicable for both hospitalized and patients who are at home to control their health status remotely.

1.6 Significance of the system

Fully implemented RPHM system is very important in our country Ethiopian since most of our people are living in rural areas where healthcare service is very limited. Hospitals are found only at the center and getting fully service of it are very challenging specially during this era than ever before. This why we propose IoT based remote health monitoring and patients' early treatment system using Arduino uno. This will not only cut down the cost of regular checkups with their doctors but also reduce the traffic congestion of hospitals.

2. Literature review

2.1 Overview of Smart Health

IoT in the health monitoring system has given us a big advantage in the development of modern medical treatment [9]. Due to advances in VLSI technology, the sensors have become smaller which has enabled the development of wearable solutions. Due to consistent internet connectivity, the devices are becoming more efficient and powerful. IoT based health monitoring devices monitor a patient 24/7. At any crucial moment, the devices generate necessary signals by analyzing statistical data [10]. As IoT based devices are constantly connected to the internet, the patients can be remotely monitored and necessary measures can be taken in case of an emergency. IoT based devices can thus provide both detection and emergency response services.

2.2 Overview of IoT

Internet of Things (IoT) is here to change the world we know. Smart cars, smart homes, smart cities, everything around us can be turned into a smart device with the help of Internet of Things. IoT sure does bring the coolness factor to technology. While IoT is poised to bring the next big boom in the job market, lack of skill is citing the biggest barrier for companies looking to implement this technology. To be considered in any of the roles mentioned earlier, you'll need to be industry ready. One workable view frames IoT as the use of network-connected devices, embedded in the physical environment, to improve some existing process or to enable a new scenario not previously possible.

These devices, or *things*, connect to the network to provide information they gather from the environment through sensors, or to allow other systems to reach out and act on the world through actuators. They could be connected versions of common objects you might already be familiar with, or new and purpose-built devices for functions not yet realized. They could be devices that you own personally and carry with you or keep in your home, or they could be embedded in factory equipment, or part of the fabric of the city you live in. Each of them is able to convert valuable information from the real world into digital data that provides increased visibility into how your users interact with your products, services, or applications.

2.3 Related Work

In [6] the architecture of the Patient Health Monitoring System (PHMS) using IoT devices is proposed to collect the required parameters and evaluate the data obtained from the IoT devices. PHMS also notifies the patient with possible precautionary measures to be practiced by them. This system suggests the patient with medical care and next step to be followed in case of critical situation. The PHMS system is evaluated for certain parameters and the decisions made on the data obtained from the source are assumed to evaluate the system. In this system Arduino uno device is proposed to collect the required parameters like temperature, heart beat and blood pressure and evaluate the data obtained from the IoT devices. It offers a complete and self-contained Wi-Fi networking solution; it can be used to host the application or to offload Wi-Fi networking functions from another application processor. This System is totally depending on Wi-Fi networking. However, there is a case in which the patient is outside of the Wi-Fi range, but still his/her health status needs to be notified. Meaning the patients' needs to know their health status

by any means from either the Doctor's web portal or from Arduino Uno in which GSM module is integrated.

Cost Effective Remote Health Monitoring System Based on IoT Using Arduino UNO is proposed in [7]. The proposed system consists mainly of two sensors- DS18B20 (Temperature sensor) and KG011 (Pulse rate sensor) connected to Arduino UNO. It does not have an inbuilt module for internet connectivity therefore, Arduino Ethernet Shield is used which is mounted at the top of Arduino board to connect the complete system with internet. The health parameters of a person sensed by the sensors are sent to the cloud with the help of Ethernet shield and from the cloud, it can be fetched on the mobile application on the person's side. Blynk app is downloaded and installed on the android and ios mobile phones. Data can be displayed in the form of graphs, tables or just the values being displayed one after another by using widgets already available in Blynk.

In this System Arduino Uno is responsible for both data acquisition from sensor and processing of these data as well, lacking processing and analyze of the data at cloud.

IoT Based Real-Time Remote Patient Monitoring System is proposed in [8]. This paper proposed an IoT based real-time electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring system that is able to support both real-time and store-and-forward modes. The store-and-forward mode has no data integrity issue and it also does not require high network quality. However, the real-time mode is challenging because transmission delay and packet loss during real-time transmission will affect the data integrity, especially for real-time ECG signal transmission. Inaccurate health data might lead to misdiagnosis.

An IoT based Patient Health Monitoring System using Arduino UNO, proposed by Kaveri S, Lincey Veronica A, Monisha H, Aarthy Suganthi Kani [11] Come up with architecture that collects the sensor data through Arduino microcontroller and stores it to the cloud where it is processed and analyzed for remote viewing. Feedback actions based on the analyzed data can be sent back to the doctor or guardian through Email and/or SMS alerts in case of any emergencies. This paper used only for temperature and pulse rate sensors.

More over all of the above papers were failed to set schedule for patients when and where they will come for treatment based the stage of illness to prevent overcrowding at hospitals and failed

to track patient's location using GPS module in order to recommend patients to buy appropriate drug nearby for low risk diseases.

3. Methodology

3.1 Framework of RPHM System

The proposed IoT based remote health monitoring and patient's early treatment will use Arduino Uno micro controller to interface all sensors that collects patient's vital parameters such as disease symptoms. In this System body temperature sensor, blood pressure sensor, heart beat sensor, and TB sensor including BMI sensor and glucose level sensor will be used in order to collect patient data. A data collected by these sensors are passed to the Arduino uno micro controller and uploaded to the cloud server which is called ThingSpeak cloud server. We will use a GSM module to send SMS to alerts doctors or patients in case of emergency. GPS module will also be attached to locate from where the sensors data will come, hence identify the patient's location in order to recommend appropriate drug to get nearby clinic. Also, any increase or decrease in parameter values can be detected and hence doctors can access cloud database to implement necessary medications immediately. This study will use ESP8266 Wi-Fi module in order to forward patient's vital information from Arduino Uno to ThingSpeak server. In case the patient is outside of Wi-Fi range or unable to access ThingSpeak cloud due to lack of smart phone he/she will be notified using SMS message. Those who have smart phone they can access cloud server using the developed mobile application and they will also be informed by email from Doctor's web portal.

The block diagram of the proposed methodology is given below:

Figure 3.1: Proposed system architecture

3.2 IoT Database ThingSpeak.com

ThingSpeak is an Internet of Things (IoT) platform that lets you collect and store sensor data in the cloud and develop IoT applications. The ThingSpeak IoT platform provides apps that let you analyze and visualize your data in MATLAB, and then act on the data. Sensor data can be sent to ThingSpeak from Arduino, Raspberry Pi, Beagle Bone Black, and other hardware. But in our case Sensor data can be sent to ThingSpeak from Arduino Uno.

The following are the steps to use thingspeak.com:

Step1: Collect the data in the new channel- Create a channel, collect data and write it to a new channel.

Step2: Analyze your data- Analyze and visualize data using MATLAB®.

Step3: Act on your data- Set threshold limits on data to send a tweet under certain conditions.[12]

3.3 Integration of IoT with Cloud Database

Cloud computing and IoT are the emerging technology, both these technologies have their advantages, however several mutual advantages can be foreseen from their integration. On one hand, IoT can address its technological constraints such as storage, processing and energy by providing the unlimited capabilities and resources of Cloud. For the success of RPHM we need to integrate our system to cloud database. From its fundamentals, the Cloud acts as an intermediate between things and applications, in order to hide all the complexities and functionalities necessary for running the application. Below are some of the factors that led to the merging of Cloud and IoT:

- Storage
- Capacity
- Computation power
- Communication resources
- Scalability
- Availability
- Interoperability

3.4 Work Plan

We have estimated the total time to complete the work and divided the total work load into steps as shown in the figure below. The Gantt chart below shows a rough estimation of the sequence with which the study work will be performed. This Gantt chart is subject to change depending on the completion time of gathering the data from where health issue is very critical in which the system must be implemented along with the availability of budget required to purchase the necessary hardware like sensors, Microcontroller and other devices that are needed to complete this study.

Table 1: Gantt chart for Workplan

ID	Task Name	Month 1&2	Month 3&4	Month 5&6	Month 7
1	Literature Survey	[Gantt bar spanning from start of Month 1 to end of Month 6]			
2	Data collection from where health issue is critical	[Gantt bar spanning from start of Month 2 to end of Month 3]			
3	Implementation		[Gantt bar spanning from start of Month 3 to end of Month 6]		
4	Testing			[Gantt bar spanning from start of Month 5 to end of Month 6]	
5	Report & Publication				[Gantt bar spanning from start of Month 7 to end of Month 7]

3.5 Hardware and Software requirements

3.5.1 Hardware Requirement

- Arduino Uno Microcontroller
- Blood Pressure Sensor (Sphygmomanometer)
- Body Temperature sensor (DERMALOG)
- Pulse Sensor (Heart beat Sensor)
- Breath Sensor for Tuberculosis
- Connecting wires
- LCD Display
- Either laptop or Desktop Computer

3.5.2 Software Requirement

1. ARDUINO IDE

An integrated development environment (IDE) (also known as integrated design environment or integrated debugging environment) is a software application that provides comprehensive facilities to computer programmers for software development. An IDE normally consists of:

- A source code editor
- A compiler/or an interpreter
- Build automation tools
- A debugger

2. MATLAB® Software to Analyze and visualize Sensor data

4. References

- [1] <https://www.britannica.com/place/Ethiopia/Health-and-welfare/>. Accessed date: June 20,2020
- [2] Worldometer<https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/ethiopia-population/>. Accessed date: June,29,2020.
- [3] Kaveri S, Lincey Veronica A, Monisha H, Aarthy Suganthi Kani,” An IOT based Patient Health Monitoring System using Arduino UNO” National Conference on Communication and Image Processing, 2019.
- [4] H. T. Yew, Y. Aditya, H. Satrial, E. Supriyanto, and Y. W. Hau, “Telecardiology system for fourth generation heterogeneous wireless networks,” *ARPJ. Eng. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 10, no. 2, 2015.
- [5] Nayyar, A., & Puri, V., “A review of Arduino board's, Lilypad's & Arduino shield”, 3rd IEEE International Conference in Computing for Sustainable Global Development (INDIACom), March 2016, pp.1485-1492.
- [6] V.Akhila, Y.Vasavi, K.Nissie, P.Venkat Rao, An IoT based Patient Health Monitoring System using Arduino Uno, International Journal of Research in Information Technology, Volume 1, Issue 1, November 2017, Pg: 1-9
- [7] Amandeep Kaur and Ashish Jasuja, Cost Effective Remote Health Monitoring System Based on IoT Using Arduino UNO, Advances in Computer Science and Information Technology (ACSIT) p-ISSN: 2393-9907; e-ISSN: 2393-9915; Volume 4, Issue 2; January-March, 2017, pp. 80-84
- [8] Hoe Tung Yew, Seng Kheau Chung, Ming Fung Ng, Ali Chekima, Soh Zhi Ping, Jamal A. Dargham, IoT Based Real-Time Remote Patient Monitoring System, IEEE International Colloquium on Signal Processing & its Applications (CSPA 2020), 28-29 Feb. 2020, Langkawi, Malaysia.
- [9] Raj, C., Jain, C., Arif, W. (2017). HEMAN: Health monitoring and nous: An IoT based ehealth care system for remote telemedicine. 2017 International Conference on Wireless Communications, Signal Processing and Networking (WiSPNET), pp. 2115-2119. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/WiSPNET.2017.8300134>.
- [10] Raj, C., Jain, C., Arif, W. (2017). HEMAN: Health monitoring and nous: An IoT based ehealth care system for remote telemedicine. 2017 International Conference on Wireless Communications, Signal Processing and Networking (WiSPNET), pp. 2115-2119. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/WiSPNET.2017.8300134>.
- [11] Kaveri S, Lincey Veronica A, Monisha H, Aarthy Suganthi Kani, An IOT based Patient Health Monitoring System using Arduino UNO. NCCIP 2019 National Conference on Communication and Image Processing.
- [12] V.Akhila, Y.Vasavi, K.Nissie, P.Venkat Rao, An IoT based Patient Health Monitoring System using Arduino Uno, International Journal of Research in Information Technology, Volume 1, Issue 1, November 2017, Pg: 3-5.